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Paper-IV

Project Report

On

**STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF δ
PHASE CsPbI_3 NANORODS BY SOLUTION PHASE SYNTHESIS**

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DECLARATION

The project work entitled “**Structural and optical characterization of δ phase CsPbI₃ nanorods by solution phase synthesis**” has been successfully carried out by me under the supervision and guidance of **Prof. K. GOPALAKRISHNA NAIK**, Department of Studies in Physics. This dissertation is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of degree of Master of Science in Physics by Mangalore University during the academic year 2017-18. I also declare that the matter embodied in the report has not been submitted previously by anybody for the award of any degree or diploma to any other university.

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**STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL
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OF δ PHASE CsPbI₃ NANORODS
BY SOLUTION PHASE SYNTHESIS**

ABSTRACT:

The main objective of this report is to synthesis and characterize room temperature Cesium Lead Iodide perovskite (CsPbI_3) nanorods (NRs) based on the solution-phase method. In the recent years perovskite Cesium Lead Halide Nanoparticles (NPs) are considered to be attractive materials for optoelectronic applications and highly efficient photovoltaic cell applications. CsPbI_3 NRs prepared via a reported approach developed by Protesescu *et al.*; SEM image and XRD data confirms the formation of orthorhombic structure.

Why we are choosing the inorganic-lead halide perovskite material?

Perovskite-related halides are important crystal structures as they possess a number of interesting properties, such as electron-acceptor behavior; a large optical transmission domain; high resistivity; antiferromagnetic; exceptional magnetic; piezoelectric; photo luminescent properties; anionic conductivity over a wide temperature range (Sarukura *et al.*, 2007; Zhang *et al.*, 2008). Both organic and inorganic lead halides ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) has tremendously researched from 2009 onwards because of their above-mentioned properties, especially their high light absorbing layer in photovoltaic cells and photoluminescence in entire visible region as light emitting applications. However, inorganic metal halides take the advantages over an organic metal halide due to their non degradation upon contact with moisture, thermal stability, as well as light-induced trap-state formation and halide segregation in the case of “mixed halide” perovskites $\text{MAPbBr}_x\text{I}_{(3-x)}$. So, in our report we discuss about properties and solution phase synthesis of inorganic metal halide nanoparticles i.e. CsPbI_3 nanorods.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Energy from solar cell is an environment friendly form of energy which is the most discussed research topic nowadays and the trend is to find a material that can produce with less cost, and are flexible and more efficient devices[1-3]. Organic perovskite materials are less expensive but even lesser expensive inorganic materials can also be used for the manufacturing of devices. Nanocrystals play an important role in these devices by quantum mechanical processes. Nanomaterials are the one whose dimension is of 10^{-9} m, and can be synthesized top down or bottom up principles. Nanomaterials with respect to their size can be 0 dimensional (Q-dots), 1D (nanowires) or 2D (thin films), and the size there by the properties can be tuned by the temperature, components used for the synthesis, etc. Here we are describing how to synthesis and characterize CsPbI₃ nanorods using the solution phase synthesis method. Solution phase synthesis refers to nanowire growth in solution. It has the advantage that it can produce nanowires in large quantity compared to other techniques like VLS, suspension, DNA template, vapor phase, anionic exchange etc.

1.1 Perovskite materials:

The general chemical formula for perovskite is AMX₃ with different sized Anion A and cations M, belonging to carbon family like Ge, Sn, Pb and X as halogen anion. A is larger than M. The structure is depicted in Fig.1.1a. Their crystallographic stability and probable structure can be described by tolerance factor t and octahedral part μ .

1.1A. Formation and tuning the structure of perovskite:

When A, M, X components fit together neatly in the crystal lattice it gives 3D. Assuming ionic radii of R_A , R_M , R_X , for a closely packed cubic perovskite structure is possible provided-

$$(R_M + R_X) = \frac{R_A + R_X}{t2^{1/2}}$$

Where t is a non definite tolerance factor (Goldschmidt's tolerance factor t), runs from 0.75 to 1.0, which relates to the strain that lattice can tolerate before the point till which it will not form. It is not a sufficient condition that $t = 0.75-1.00$ for the formation of the perovskite structure. For some systems whose t is within the range of 0.8 to 0.9, perovskite structure is not stable[4]. Additional parameters are, therefore, necessary for the prediction of perovskite formation. It is well known that the octahedron BO_6 is the basic mosaic or unit for perovskite structure. If one cation and six anions form an octahedron, the ratio of their ionic radius (R_M/R_O) is reported within a limited range, this factor is defined as the octahedral factor, μ given by-

$$\mu = \frac{R_B}{R_X}$$

So, it is needed to try to construct a structural map by the tolerance factor and the octahedral factor for perovskite formability[5].

High temperature phase will be cubic and low temperature less symmetry tetragonal or orthorhombic[6]. CsPbI_3 should be in an ideal cubic phase at 310°C but the lattice relaxed and distorted due to quenching forming an orthorhombic perovskite structure Fig.1.1b.

Fig.1.1: a) Cubic (or normal) perovskite structure b) Orthorhombic delta phase CsPbI₃ structure.

All-inorganic cesium lead halide perovskite nanocrystals were first reported by Kovalenko and co-workers in 2015[7] with excellent optical and electronic properties[8-10]. Recently, all-inorganic lead halide perovskite colloidal nanocrystals have been successfully synthesized with high photoluminescence quantum yields (PLQY) and tunable emission spectra covering the entire visible spectral range which have potential uses in light-emitting diodes, solar cells, and tunable lasers [11-15]. Despite of these pioneering works, the instability of nanocrystalline perovskites is a major demerit for the photovoltaic.

1.2 Why CsPbI₃

Organic Perovskite such as MAPbI₃(MA-Methylamine), can only function for a few minutes or hours [16]. In general, Cs-based perovskite materials are more stable than those based on organic cations. Until now, perovskite nanocrystals with different shapes such as nanocubes [17], nanowires [18], and nanosheets[14], have been prepared by hot injection, anion exchange, solvothermal, room-temperature re-precipitation, and

ultrasonication [6-10]. Solution phase synthesis was first done by Zhang, D. D.; Eaton, S. W.; Yu, Y.; Dou, L. T.; Yang, P. D. for CsPbI₃ in 2015.

Kulbak [16] showed that inorganic CsPbBr₃ has excellent thermal stability in the orthorhombic phase (δ -phase) and it has a 2.25eV band gap, this limits its application for solar cells and optoelectronics as it lies in the red spectral region. Two types of the structural phase transition of non-perovskite Y (yellow)-CsPbI₃ (δ -phase) and perovskite B (black)-CsPbI₃ (α -phase) nanowires are observed by the scientists. In air at room temperature the black CsPbI₃ undergoes a rapid phase-transition to a nonfunctional, non perovskite structure, known as the “yellow phase”. Unlike the cubic perovskite structure in which the metal–halide octahedra share corners, the orthorhombic yellow phase is comprised of 1D chains of edge-sharing octahedral [19]. The incorporation of iodide allows the band edge to be red shifted, and the cubic phase (α -phase) of CsPbI₃ has a band gap of 1.73 eV, is close to the ideal level for a tandem solar cell. Thus, CsPbI₃ shows the unique combination of a suitable band gap, high quantum efficiency, and long radiative lifetime for photovoltaic applications. However, at room temperature, α -CsPbI₃ undergoes an undesired transition to a yellowish, insulating δ -phase [14], and α -CsPbI₃ is only the preferred thermodynamic structure above 315 °C [20, 21] which is formed at high temperature with the conditions that the cubic perovskite geometry is the equilibrium phase [22]. Perovskite B-CsPbI₃ nanowires showed a lower bandgap, stronger PL emission, and higher photoconductance than the Y-CsPbI₃ phase. Band gap goes from 2.69 eV to 1.7 eV and emission range for yellow from 300-700 and 600-700 for black [23]. For CsPbI₃, t is 0.81, which limits its black-phase stability. Currently, the question of “how to stabilize perovskite phase of CsPbI₃ at room temperature” is a primary challenge for the research community.

A unique feature of metal halide perovskites, compared to crystalline Si and GaAs, is their high crystallinity despite low temperature processing (200 °C). This enables to process on a range of substrates, and versatile forms of perovskite materials nano to macro can be created with ease.

CsPbX₃ NCs crystallize into cubic phase at room temperature while the CsPbX₃ nanowires show orthorhombic phase, which shows the importance of synthetic conditions, size, and shape of the nanostructures on the crystal phase transitions [24].

BAND GAP: The minima of conduction bands (CB) and the maxima of valence bands (VB) are at R symmetry point. Hence these cesium based lead–halide perovskites in cubic phase have fundamental direct band gap nature at R symmetry point. Direct band gaps in these compounds can also be seen at other symmetry points M, r and X. The conduction and valence bands as well as lower valence bands are shifted towards the Fermi level. This fact is due to the increasing number of electrons in the respective bands and the occupancy of states near the Fermi level.

Here we synthesized CsPbI₃ where we got cubes in first 10 min (not cubic phase), nanowires in 1 hour of reaction time and characterized them using XRD, UV-VIS spectra and FESEM-EDS. We also realized some of the major results regarding stability of formed perovskite and reaction conditions.

CHAPTER 2

METHODS OF SYNTHESIS OF CsPbI₃

2.1 Anionic exchange method:

Materials and chemicals: Cesium carbonate (Cs_2CO_3), oleic acid (OA), 1-octadecene (ODE), ethanol (EtOH, Aldrich), oleylamine (OAm), HCl $\geq 37\%$, HBr 48%, HI 57%, lead chloride (PbCl_2), lead bromide (PbBr_2), lead iodide (PbI_2), n-trioctylphosphine (TOP), methylmagnesium chloride (MeMgCl, 3M in THF), methylmagnesium bromide (MeMgBr, 3M in ether), methylmagnesium iodide (MeMgI, 33% in ethylether, ca. 2 mol/L, TCI), toluene, hexane.

Preparation of Cs-oleate: Cs_2CO_3 (0.814 g) OA (2.5 mL) and ODE (40 mL) were added into a 100 mL 3-neck flask, dried for 1h at 120 °C and then heated under argon (Ar) to 150 °C until all Cs_2CO_3 reacted with OA. Since Cs-oleate precipitates out of ODE at room-temperature, it must be preheated to 100 °C before injection.

Preparation of oleylammonium halides (OAmX): Ethanol (100 mL) and OAm (0.038 mol) were combined in a 250 mL 2-neck flask and vigorously stirred. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-water bath and HX (0.076 mol, HCl $\geq 37\%$; HBr 48%; HI 57%) was added. The reaction mixture was left to react overnight under Arflow. Then the solvent was evaporated under vacuum and the obtained product was purified by rinsing multiple times with diethylether. The product was left under vacuum overnight in a vacuum oven at 80 °C resulting in a white powder for OAmCl and OAmBr and a dark orange waxy-powder for OAmI.

Synthesis of CsPbX_3 NCs: ODE (5 mL) and 0.188 mmol of PbX_2 (PbCl_2 – 0.052 g, ; PbBr_2 – 0.069 g, PbI_2 – 0.086 g) were loaded into a 25 mL 3-neck flask and dried under vacuum at 120 °C for 1h. Dried OA (1.5 mL for PbCl_2 , 0.5 mL for PbBr_2 and 0.7 mL for PbI_2) and OAm (1.5 mL for PbCl_2 , 0.5 mL for PbBr_2 and 0.7 mL for PbI_2) were injected at 120 °C under N_2 flow. After complete solubilisation of a PbX_2 salt, the temperature was raised to 180-190 °C and Cs-oleate solution (0.4 mL of stock

solution prepared as described above) was swiftly injected and 1 minute later the reaction mixture was cooled down by a water bath. For obtaining CsPbCl₃ NCs, a higher temperature of 170 °C and 1 mL of n-Trioctylphosphine (TOP) are necessary to solubilize PbCl₂. After reaction, the aggregated NCs were separated by centrifugation. After centrifugation, the supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was redispersed in dried toluene for further use in anion-exchange reactions.

Anion-exchange reactions. The anion exchange reactions were conducted using a Schlenk line. PbBr₂, PbI₂ and OAmX as anion sources were mixed with ODE (5 mL) in a 25 mL 3-neck flask and kept under vacuum at 120 °C for 10 minutes. Dried OA and OAm (0.2 mL each) were injected at 120 °C under N₂ flow. After complete solubilisation of the anion source, the temperature was lowered to 40 °C and CsPbX₃ NCs (20-25 mg) dispersed in toluene were injected to initiate the anion-exchange. When using PbCl₂ as the anion source, 1 mL TOP was added and it was necessary to raise the temperature to 150-170 °C for short time in order to solubilize PbCl₂. When using MeMgX as the anion source, it should be injected after the solvent and ligands are dried, just prior to addition of NCs. After reaction, the NCs were isolated by centrifugation. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was dispersed in hexane (0.3 mL) and centrifuged again. The supernatant was mixed with toluene (0.9 mL). NCs were precipitated by adding 0.3 mL acetonitrile, followed by centrifuging. The obtained precipitated NCs were redispersed in toluene for further analysis.

2.2 VLS method:

Fig2.1: Schematic illustration of vapor-liquid-solid nanowires growth mechanism including three stages alloying, nucleation, and axial growth.

The vapor-liquid-solid (VLS) mechanism, which was proposed in the 1960s for large whisker growth. Direct evidence for the nanowire growth mechanism, however, is still lacking except for the fact that these nanowires generally have alloy droplets on their tips. Three well-defined stages have been clearly identified during the process: metal alloying, crystal nucleation, and axial growth. On the basis of this mechanism study, selective growth of nanowires with different diameters has been demonstrated. Particles could generate sufficient vapor to condense onto the neighboring clusters. During the experiments, the sample stage was heated resistively to 800-900 °C.

(I): Alloying process: Clusters remain in the solid state up to our maximum experimental temperature 900°C if there is no vapor condensation. This is confirmed by selected area electron diffraction on the pure Au clusters. With increasing amount of vapor condensation and dissolution, form an alloy and liquefy. The volume of the alloy droplets increases, and the elemental contrast decreases while the alloy composition crosses sequentially, from left to right, a biphasic region (solid and liquid alloy) and a single phase region (liquid).

(II): Nucleation: Once the composition of the alloy crosses the second liquidus line, it enters another biphasic region (alloy and crystal). This is where nanowire nucleation starts. Knowing the alloy volume change, we estimate that the nucleation generally occurs at weight percentage of 50-60%. This value differs from the

composition calculated from the equilibrium phase diagram which indicates the first precipitation of crystal should occur at 40% (weight) and 800 °C.

(111)Axial growth: Once the nanocrystal nucleates at the liquid/solid interface, further condensation/dissolution of vapor into the system will increase the amount of crystal precipitation from the alloy. This can be readily accounted for, using the famous lever rule of phase diagram. The incoming species prefer to diffuse to and condense at the existing solid/liquid interface, primarily due to the fact that less energy will be involved with the crystal step growth as compared with secondary nucleation events in a finite volume. Consequently, secondary nucleation events are efficiently suppressed, and no new solid/liquid interface will be created. The existing interface will then be pushed forward (or backward) to form a nanowire. After the system cools, the alloy droplets solidify on the nanowire tips[25].

2.3Suspension method:

A suspended nanowire is a wire produced in a high vacuum chamber held at the longitudinal extremities. Suspended nanowires can be produced by chemical etching of a larger wire, bombardment of larger wire with energetic ions.

The liquid-phase synthesis of colloidal QDs involves a series of chemical reactions. Therefore, the chemical reactor in which the chemical reaction takes place is the primary consideration. The chemical reactors can be divided into two broad categories, which are batch reactors and continuous reactors. Batch reactors are used for most of the synthetic approaches of colloidal QDs carried out in a laboratory.

2.4 Solution phase synthesis: [26]

Figure 2.1. (a) Schematic diagram for a hot-injection organometallic synthesis of QDs

Here hot precursor solution is injected into a batch reactor containing MX_2 solution in the presence of surfactants. The reaction is carried out in an inert condition using standard Schlenk techniques, by reacting cesium oleate with lead halide in the presence of oleic acid and oleylamine in octadecene (ODE) at 150–250 °C. To analyze the NWs' formation mechanism, the reaction was quenched to room temperature at different points in time, and the respective intermediates were separated by centrifugation and examined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). For CsPbBr_3 NWs synthesis, the reaction dynamics have been studied at 150 °C. At the initial stage ($t < 10$ min), the reaction is dominated by the formation of nanocubes (NCs).

With increasing time, more NWs form while the amount of NCs decreases; in addition, there present some square-shaped nanosheet

2.5 Colloidal phase Synthesis Method ⁽³⁴⁾

The perovskite nanoparticles were prepared using a simple and reliable preparation method in which a mixture of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$ and a medium or long chain alkyl ammonium bromide was reacted with PbI_2 in the presence of oleic acid and octadecene. This is followed by the addition of acetone which induced the precipitation of a yellow solid from the solution. The methylammonium salt and the lead bromide had previously been dissolved in a small amount of dimethylformamide (DMF) to improve their solubility in the media.

Here The methyl ammonium cations are embedded in the voids of a set of corner-sharing PbX_6 octahedra with their chains dangling outside it would act as the capping ligands of the nanoparticle which limits the growth of the array extending in three dimensions hence stabilizes the nanoparticles produced. It is proved that long alkyl chain cations acts as better capping ligands in isolation of the nanoparticles core. A good organic capping agent, such as long alkyl chain amines, would favor the formation of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbX}_3$ nanoparticles, which would eventually be dispersible in aprotic solvents. Hence the long chain ammonium salt played a key role in the formation of the hybrid perovskite nanoparticles and in their capacity to give rise to colloidal solutions. Highly fluorescent thin films and first electroluminescent devices were prepared using the colloidal solution of these nanoparticles.

In the colloidal synthesis approach to CsPbX_3 nano platelets the reaction mixture will remain unreacted at room temperature until it is triggered by the addition of Acetone which initiates the nucleation and growth process. The CsPbX_3 is prepared by hot injection method i.e. by injecting hot solution of cesium oleate to PbX_3 solution at high temperature. The size of QDs can be controlled by varying the reaction temperature and time. The luminescence wavelength can be tuned by varying the size of QDs or by changing the halide composites.

2.6 Synthesis of Cesium Lead Halide Perovskite Nanocrystals in a Droplet-Based Micro fluidic Platform: ⁽³³⁾

Micro fluidic reaction systems are adept in transferring mass and energy rapidly, allowing the creation or homogenization of both temperature and reagent gradients on ultra short time scales. Facile and fast variation of precursor volumetric flow rates and the ability to sequentially add reagents in a controlled manner enable the production of NCs with varying and complex composition, as well as rapid, accurate, reproducible, and economic screening of parameters.

Fig. 2.3 (a) Illustration of the droplet-based microfluidic platform integrated with online absorbance and fluorescence detection for the synthesis and real time characterization of CsPbX₃ perovskite NCs.(b) Image of the generated droplets after exiting the heating zone taken under UV excitation ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$), showing bright PL of CsPbX₃ NCs

Many researchers have recognized the significance of micro fluidics in NC synthesis, demonstrating the synthesis of a large variety of colloidal semiconductors, metals and metal oxides. We designed a rather simple setup for studying the formation of CsPbX_3 NCs as in fig. In this setup, the precursors (loaded into precision syringe pumps) are rapidly mixed using a cross-mixing junction and form droplets that can be rapidly heated to the desired reaction temperature. For mixed halide $\text{CsPb}(X/Y)_3$ systems (where X and Y are the two halides), PbX_2 and PbY_2 precursor solutions are premixed at a T-junction mixer before delivering them into the cross-mixer. With T- and cross junctions, the Pb/Cs molar ratio R_1 and halide molar ratios R_2 (Br/Cl or I/Br) can be adjusted continuously and independently, generating droplets of various compositions. Control over the reaction time is achieved by controlling the residence time of the droplet in the heated zone. Reaction time dependent optical measurements are accomplished by spiral rotation of the heating rod with respect to stationary fiber optics for online measurements of the absorption and emission spectra. Presented reaction times were calculated using the superficial flow rates of the fluids. Control experiment using high-speed imaging of droplets showed deviation of less than 10% from the calculated rate. Within the droplets, the complete mixing of precursors occurs in less than 300 ms, as can be seen from the control experiment using a quenching assay of fluorescein/iodide system. This time for mixing is allowed before the droplets enter the heating stage. We recorded early-stage kinetics within 0.1–10 s from the moment droplets enter the heating stage, as it take up to 100 ms for heating ramp.

CHAPTER 3
SYNTHESIS PROCEDURE AND
CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 Chemicals: Cs_2CO_3 (Molychem), Octadecene (ODE,Kemphasol), Oleic Acid (OA,Molychem), PbI_2 (Kemphasol), Oleylamine(SRL/Pallav), Hexane AR (Molychem). All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

Fig.3.1: a)Experimental apparatus used b)Settings done in the three neck flask.

The preparation of CsPbI_3 nanowires was done in inert atmosphere (Ar atmosphere) using schlenk technique which we made by our own which is schematically shown in Fig.3.1a and Fig.3.1b shows the settings in three neck flask. Reaction of freshly prepared cesium oleate which is then injected into reaction mixture of lead iodide and octadecene which gives various types of nanocrystals as the reaction time proceeds. A schematic representation of steps is in Fig.3.2.

Fig.3.2: Various steps involved in the synthesis of CsPbI_3

3.2 Preparation of Cs-oleate solution: 0.4 g Cs_2CO_3 and 1.2 mL OA, 15 mL ODE, were put into 3-neck flask along with the degassing process, the solution had no color and slowly it attained light yellow and dried under vacuum at 120 °C for 1h. Then it is heated under inert atmosphere where we used argon gas at 150 °C until all Cs_2CO_3 reacted with OA. The color changes into deep yellow and a reddish yellow color is observed at the end.

Fig.3.3. Pictures taken during the synthesis and the last image shows the final product.

Synthesis of CsPbX_3 nanorods: We used the following different ways of synthesis TABLE1

samp le	ODE	PbI_2	OLA	OA	Cesium oleate	Reaction time	morphology
A	0	0.069g	0.5ml	0.8ml	0.6ml	90min	Thick Nanorods
B	5ml	0.069g	0.5ml	0.8ml	0.6ml	60min	Thin Nanorods
C	5ml	0.071g	0.5ml	0.8ml	0.6ml	10min	Nanocubes
D	5ml	0.071g	0.5ml	0.8ml	0.6ml	30min	Nanocubes&rods

TABLE1- Different ways of synthesis of nanorods used.

Synthesis of CsPbX₃ nanowires: ODE and PbI₂ were loaded into a 3-neckflask and degassed under vacuum for 1 h at 120 °C. 0.5 mL OLA and 0.8mL OA were injected at 120 °C under argon. Slight yellow and then golden yellow color is observed. Then at 150 °C and 1 h was allowed for complete dissolution of the PbI₂ salt. 0.6 mL as-prepared Cs-oleate solution was quickly injected. After 5 – 10 min, the reaction mixture was cooled by an ice-water bath; a black colored solution with yellow mixed white precipitate is obtained.

Isolation and purification of CsPbX₃ nanowires: The crude solution was cooled down with a ice cold water and aggregated nanoparticles were separated by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10min and washed twice with hexane [7].

The characterization of the sample A,B,C and D was done by XRD at scanning rate 2⁰ using XRD instrument at Mangalore University, UV-VIS spectra was taken at PURSE lab Mangalore University, FESEM-EDS was done at CeNS lab Bangalore.

3.3 CHARACTERIZATION:

Structural and optical characterization of CsPbI₃ samples

Objectives:

- I. Determine the crystal structure
- II. Determine the energy gap
- III. Checking the formation of nanorod growth

3.31 Determination of crystal structure by X-ray diffraction method

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) is a rapid analytical technique primarily used for phase identification of a crystalline material and can provide information on unit cell dimensions. The analyzed material is finely ground, homogenized, and average bulk composition is determined.

Max von Laue and Co-workers, in 1912, discovered that crystalline substances act as three-dimensional diffraction gratings for X-ray wavelengths similar to the spacing of planes in a crystal lattice. X-ray diffraction is now a common technique for the study of crystal structures and atomic spacing. X-ray diffraction is based on constructive interference of monochromatic X-rays and a crystalline sample. These X-rays are generated by a cathode ray tube, filtered to produce monochromatic radiation, collimated to concentrate, and directed toward the sample (Figure 3.3). (we used Benchtop X-ray diffraction instrument) The diffracted rays interfered constructively when Bragg's law is satisfied. i.e. $n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta$, where n is the integer, λ is the wavelength of the X rays, d is the interplanar spacing generating the diffraction, and θ is the diffraction angle.

This law relates the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation to the diffraction angle and the lattice spacing in a crystalline sample. These diffracted X-rays are then detected, processed, and counted. By scanning the sample through a range of 2θ angles, all possible diffraction directions of the lattice should be attained due to the random orientation of the powdered material. Conversion of the diffraction peaks to d -spacing allows identification of the compound because each compound has a set of unique d -spacing. Typically, this is achieved by comparison of d -spacing with standard reference patterns.

Fig.3.4:Schematic diagram of a diffractometer system.

X-ray diffraction spectra were measured on a Benchtop X-ray diffraction Diffractometer (Copper anode, $K\alpha_1 = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$, $K\alpha_2 = 1.54443 \text{ \AA}$, $K\alpha_2/K\alpha_1$ ratio = 0.50). The XRD patterns obtained for the samples are shown below.

The measured spectrum for CsPbI_3 shown here is in good agreement with JCPDS data (reference code 00-018-0378 and 01-074-1970) for the orthorhombic perovskite structure. The absence of (111) peak in all the four data show that the structure is orthorhombic[27]. Strong diffraction peaks were observed at angles 9.8, 13.9, 22.38, 25.45, 26.08, 27, 32.5, 37.46, 41.2, 53.7 indicating the orthorhombic crystal structure. Some of the prominent peaks and values of d are given in the TABLE2-

2 θ	hkl	D (Å)	2 θ	hkl	D (Å)
9.8	011	9.018	27	122	3.285
13.055	012	6.776	32.5	211	2.316
22.38	023	3.923	37.46	200	2.399
25.45	121	3.468	41.2	220	2.180
26.08	024	3.388	53.23	217	1.719

TABLE2: Prominent XRD peaks obtained

Scherer's equation gives the particle size-

Particle size, $t' = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$ Where k is 0.8 to 0.9, λ is wavelength of x ray, β is FWHM for corresponding peak at 2 θ .

We have found the particle size for most intense peak using this formula and we get the values as given in TABLE3-

sample	t'(Å)
A	21.52
B	31.4
C	176.22
D	222.32

TABLE3: Calculated particle size from XRD data

From the XRD peaks it is clear that percentage of crystallinity is 1.

The calculated lattice parameter values are $a=4.79\text{\AA}$, $b=10.45\text{\AA}$, $c=17.8\text{\AA}$ using the formula for orthorhombic

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{h^2}{a^2} + \frac{k^2}{b^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2}$$

For the samples, the intensity of the (032) (in sample B and D) and (024) (in sample C) plane was very high compared with the other planes. This shows that the CsPbI₃ nanocrystals were grown along these planes. In case of sample A, X-ray diffraction is more in plane (114), implying the growth along this plane is relatively more.

In the XRD peaks obtained, there are also one or two peaks corresponding to black phase which says that even though yellow phase is obtained, there is little amount of black phase at higher angles even though the synthesis at lower than 305°C. This corresponds to pseudocubic fraction in delta phase or coexistence of both the phases. Absence of some peaks is attributed to the preferred growth orientation.

3.32 UV-VIS SPECTRA: Determination of energy gap by UV- visible spectroscopy

Spectrophotometry is a technique that uses the absorbance of light by an analyte (the substance to be analysed) at a certain wavelength to determine the analyte concentration. UV/VIS (ultra violet/visible) spectrophotometry uses light in UV and visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Light of this wavelength is able to affect the excitation of electrons in the atomic or molecular ground state to higher energy levels, giving rise to an absorbance at wavelengths specific to each molecule. When a beam of radiation (light) passes through a substance or a solution, some of the light may be absorbed and the remainder transmitted through the sample.

The ratio of the intensity of the light entering the sample (I_0) to that exiting the sample (I) at a particular wavelength is defined as the transmittance (T). The absorbance (A) of a sample is the negative logarithm of the transmittance. $A = -\log(T)$. From the Beer-Lambert Law, the absorbance of a sample at a given wavelength is proportional to the absorptivity of the substance (a constant at each wavelength), the path length (the distance the light travels through the sample) and the concentration of the absorbing substance. In these cases, the Beer-Lambert Law holds.

$$\text{i.e. } A = a * b * c$$

Where a = the absorptivity of the substance b = path length c = concentration of the substance.

Fig.3.5: absorption of the light by sample

Observation and graphs:

Fig.3.5: UV-VIS absorbance graph obtained for sample A and sample B.

Fig.3.6: UV-VIS spectra for sample C and sample D

For UV-Visible spectroscopy, sample should be either thin film or solution of nanoparticle with known concentration. We prepared the solution of sample A and B with an isopropanol and isoctane used as a solvent and corresponding absorption curves as shown in Fig.3.5 and Fig.3.6. Absorbance curves where red and black color represents the isoctane solvent and isopropanol solvent.

Absorbance in the first two samples A and B is found to be more in the range 200nm to 400nm. In samples C and D absorbance is found to be more in the region 450nm to 800nm. Addition of ODE gives a unique peak as seen in every graph. We made UV-VIS characterization for the sample A, B, C and D after 18 hrs of the synthesis and after 13 days of the synthesis for first two samples A and

B where we found that the absorbance decreased but the peaks appeared at the same points. For sample C and D after a day of synthesis we got some broad peaks at higher wavelength region which indicates the presence of nanocubes in the sample. This also indicates the relaxing of the formed stable black phase slowly into yellow phase. The sample was made solution and also by thin film, made 3 trials all the results found to be same. Two peaks are obtained, which is due to the self trapped exciton (protesescu, 2015), one within the band other between the bands. The low energy broad peak observed has been attributed to the formation of self trapped exciton (nikl, m; nitschk, somma, 2000).

The peaks obtained are as in the following TABLE 4 using the formula-

$$E = h\nu$$

$$E = \frac{1.24 \times 10^6}{\lambda_{\max}}$$

SAMPLE	1st peak (nm)	BAND GAP(eV)	2nd peak	BAND GAP(eV)
SAMPLE A	266.7	4.657	352.7	3.521
SAMPLE B	291.2	4.265	360.6	3.444
SAMPLE C	391.4	3.173	571.7	2.172
SAMPLE D	393.8	3.154	580.0	2.141

TABLE 4: Peaks in UV absorbance spectra and corresponding exciton peaks.

In delta phase sample has indirect band gap. The sample we prepared has a band gap in the range 2.1eV to 4.65eV as seen. According to the Beer Lambert's

law, spectra depends on concentration of ligands and the lead iodide added. Also as time increases, the particle size increases and there will be variation of wavelength maximum.

3.33 SEM:

SEM images are taken for all the four samples which are shown below. One can see the nanocrystals formed in the image. For sample A the rod length is around 1000nm and diameter is around 500nm. The corresponding images of 20micro and 2micro are shown in fig. All the SEM images are taken at the CeNS Bengaluru at 10.0kV.

Fig.3.7: SEM images of sample A. FESEM images shows the nanorods growth in the sample A prepared without ODE but in shorter length.

Needle shaped nanorods with different growth direction is observed in the sample A. The inherent anisotropy of crystal structure can be seen from the image.

Fig.3.8: SEM images of sample B. FESEM image shows the relatively larger length nanorods in sample B prepared with ODE solvent.

For the sample B orthorhombic with 6 edged nanowires are formed and the growth direction is same for all the wires. SEM images of sample B, thus show that the perovskite sample prepared over here is nanowires that have sizes in the scale bars of 500 nm.

Fig.3.81: SEM images of sample C

For sample C nanorods of 100nm to 150nm are obtained.

Fig.3.82: SEM images of sample D

For sample D nanorods of 100nm to 150nm are obtained.

Finally, we can conclude from FESEM image is that the solution-phase synthesis method gives the best nanorods growth for δ -CsPbI₃ phase only when both ODE and OLA are used as surfactants and also with increase in the reaction temperature like 10 mins, 30 mins and 60 mins for the samples C, D and B respectively the outer surface of the nanorods goes on increases (looking at the FESEM image of 500nm scale).

3.34 EDS:

Fig.3.9: EDS spectra of the sample.

Data from EDS is given in TABLE5-

Element	Series[wt.%]	unn. [at.%]	C norm. [wt.%]	C Atom.	(3 Sigma)
Cesium	L-series	21.31	26.92	28.51	2.76
Lead	L-series	17.60	22.23	15.10	2.29
Iodine	M-series	40.26	50.85	56.39	4.55
Total:		79.17	100.00	100.00	

TABLE5: EDS data for the sample.

EDS data shows the proportions of the respective elements, and is in match with the added amount.

CHAPTER 4
CONCLUSION AND FUTURE OF THE
PEROVSKITE WORLD

4.1 CONCLUSION:

As the color of sample A which is carried out without ODE for 90 min is white, indicates that ODE increases the kinetics of the reaction, that then for sample B we got good thinner NRs. We thus concluded that the key parameters controlling nanorod formation are the reaction temperature, concentration of the reactants, and time to which reaction is carried out. The peaks obtained from the XRD data shows that the sample is polycrystalline and is in orthorhombic structure. UV-VIS spectra are obtained twice that is within a day of synthesis and after two weeks of the synthesis and we observed that there is a initiation of degradation of UV-VIS absorbance peaks after two weeks. But the degradation is too slow that the peaks are still observed at the same wavelength value but the absorbance value started to decay. Thus we conclude that the yellow phase is stable. SEM image shows that when the octadecene is not taking its part in the synthesis , which is in the sample A, the reaction is not complete that one obtains a nanorod with a needle shape that the reaction to be continued for still next few hours to obtain nanowires. Thus, in sample B where we added octadecene increases the reaction kinetics that we obtained thinner nanorods too early. In sample C and D we got average sized nanorods indicating that the time is an essential parameter for the formation of nanorods. The SEM images show the thinner and thicker nanorods, and one can clearly visualize the six edged orthorhombic structure. From the EDS data it is clear that the cesium lead halide formed is in correct proportion.

4.2 Future perspectives in electronic devices:

Perovskite materials have a good future in optoelectronic devices especially in cheaper solar cells[22], LEDs[28], photodetectors[29] and nanolasers[41]. In perovskite materials cesium lead halide as discussed in the introduction, is less expensive than the other organic perovskite devices.

Properties of CsPbI_3 like Optimal band gaps, high absorption coefficients, and long-range exciton diffusion lengths will result in good solar cell device. The well-functioning planar junction devices demonstrate long-range electron and hole transport in this material. The cesium lead halide being all inorganic perovskite has lower thermal decomposition. One more question about cesium lead halide solar cells is about its solar light absorbing capacity and about the efficiency. So far 6.5% efficiency is found (Rachel E. Beal, Daniel J. Slotcavage) the value of band gap that a material need to have in order to replace the silicon solar cells is around 1.9eV, when CsPbX_3 doped with methylamine the band gap can be tuned between 2.3eV to 1.6eV. Cesium lead halide itself can be tuned over this range[20], thus either of the ways one gets a good substitution for silicon which can show a new revolution in solar cell energy. When it comes for stability, lead is very sensitive to atmosphere and moisture.

Fig.4.1: This image shows that how easy it is to make solar cells of perovskite.

Fig.4.2: CsPbI₃ Solar cell (from Q-dots)

CsPbI₃ is considered as one of the most promising candidates for achieving stable structure because the radius of Cs is able to provide an appropriate tolerance factor of the lead halide perovskite. A strategy for incorporating a large radius cation into inorganic CsPbI₃ perovskite structure that could effectively modulate phase transition temperature and enhance the α -phase stability at ambient environment. They found that these new derived Cs_xPEA_{1-x}PbI₃ (phenmethylammonium:PEA) films possess low dimensional features of quasi-2D perovskite through analyzing their optical properties. By partially replacing Cs⁺ with PEA⁺ cations, a series of quasi-2D Cs_xPEA_{1-x}PbI₃ perovskite films was symmetrically studied. Incorporating the PEA⁺ cation effectively improves both film morphology and optoelectronic properties. An optimal composition retains the stability of the Cs_xPEA_{1-x}PbI₃ perovskite film in black α phase in air, and it also enhances the phase transition temperature up to 250 °C. Solar cells based on the Cs_{0.9}PEA_{0.1}PbI₃ absorbing layer exhibits a PCE of 5.7%. The concept of using large ionic radius cations provides a promising strategy for tailoring 3D perovskite materials and this study will further contribute to overcoming the stability issues of perovskite devices.

CsPbX₃ NCs exhibited bright luminescence with quantum yields up to 90% and narrow emission wavelengths that were tuned over the entire visible region depending on the NCs size and halide ion composition. This prompted materials scientists to utilize

these NCs for various optoelectronic applications. Amplified spontaneous emission and tunable electroluminescence have been demonstrated from these NCs.

Fig.4.3: CsPbI₃ Perovskite photodetector

photodetector devices[29] with CsPbI₃NCs films. As they have a relatively longer radiative lifetime than the green and blue emitting NCs, choose red emitting CsPbI₃ NCs could be beneficial in producing large photocurrents. Photodetectors fabricated from CsPbI₃ NCs exhibited the good on/off photocurrent ratio of 105 and rise and decay times of 24 and 29 ms[30].

LEDs by CsPbI₃ is done by emre, sergant and team due to the poor colloidal stability of [Fengjia Fan, Jun Pan, Sjoerd Hoogland, Riccardo Comin, Osman M. Bakr, Lazaro A. Padilha, Ana F. Nogueira, and Edward H. Sargent*]

A nonpolar solvent method was reported for CsPbX₃ PQDs in which PbX₂ salts were solubilized in oleylamine/OA capping agents. Overcome the reliance on oleylamine and the requirement of multiple competitive ligands, turned instead to Cs-oleate (CsOA) and Pb-oleate (PbOA₂) and searched for a new halide source. Wei et al. reported a room-temperature synthetic method based on carboxylic acid capped CsPbBr₃ PQDs. PQDs show degraded PLQY properties within 2–3 days and, suffered from lower PLQY for above room temperature reactions. The PQDs show PLQY up to 70%, narrow emission spectra, and enhanced colloidal stability. These PQDs are more stable upon purification with polar solvents, an advance that we attribute to stronger ligand attachment. Red, green, and blue (RGB) PQD LED using first time solution-processed polymer-based hole transport layers in an inverted LED structure for PQDs is been fabricated. Green and blue

LEDs show a threefold increase in performance for green, and tenfold for blue LED efficiencies compared to prior related reports for amine/ammonium-capped cross-linked PQDs. The absence of oleylamine also accelerates the growth reaction of PQDs. Device turn-on voltages were between 2.6 and 4 V depending on the PQD type (Figure 4d). The corresponding peak external quantum efficiency (EQE) values are 0.05%, 0.325%, and 0.075% for RGB devices, respectively. Green and blue LEDs show a threefold increase in performance for green, and tenfold for blue LED efficiencies compared to prior related reports for amine/ammonium capped cross-linked PQDs. The relatively low EQE value of the blue-emitting device is seen. An amine-free synthesis for PQDs stabilized solely by oleic acid, enabled by the choice of a novel halide precursor is also fabricated. Oleic acid capped PQDs showed improved colloidal stability and provided high stability against polar solvents during purification. This allows solution-processed conductive PQD films with low organic content and increased stability. A new LED device architecture by utilizing a solution-processed polymer-based hole transport layer with highly comparable RGB LED performances is been reported. Further optimization of the synthesis and device fabrication of perovskite quantum dots is the subject of ongoing investigation, in particular, the core-shell structures to reduce the Auger recombination losses.

Fig.4.4: Perovskite LED.

Here we shall list most common applications for other perovskites:

- (a) Thermo power generation;
- (b) Ion conductors in fuel cells/sensors;
- (c) Catalytic materials. Co-based perovskite material is as a replacement for Pt in catalytic converters in diesel vehicles;

Even though all the research show that cesium lead halide perovskite is having many applications in optoelectronics and is cheaper to synthesis, still it has some disadvantages which makes scientists to work more about it. There are commercialization and stability challenges. Highest PCE is got by lead that is toxic, and are reported to be sensitive to humidity and oxygen. One needs to find a substitution for lead. Tin can replace lead, which has found (noel et al, 2004) 6.4% efficiency, but Sn^{2+} conversion into Sn^{4+} needed to be found a solution.

The cheapest solar cell that can be prepared, the easiest way one can device photovoltaic and other important optoelectronic devices, yes perovskite cesium lead iodide is the answer.

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